

Studies in Formation and Properties of Carbon-Halogen Surface Complexes. Part I. Interaction of Charcoal and Chlorine Gas

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Reaction of chlorine gas with different samples of sugar charcoal, containing varying amounts of combined oxygen and hydrogen, at different temperatures has been found to involve formation of hydrochloric acid gas and fixation of chlorine, the former being always in excess of the latter. The magnitude of each reaction increases with time up to 6 hours and with temperature up to 400-500°. The reactions follow monomolecular trends in presence of excess of chlorine.

A maximum of about 24% chlorine can be fixed on the original and 400°-degassed charcoals. The amount decreases on degassing the charcoal at higher temperatures, presumably on account of progressive decrease in the hydrogen content. The reaction appears to be more of substitutive than of additive type. The elimination of hydrogen from the original charcoal on treatment with chlorine at increasing temperatures indicates that hydrogen is bonded with different energy levels which are not continuous. Probably, only a part of the hydrogen is present along the surface and the rest of it is present in more than one layers in the interior of the particles. Only a small amount of the hydrogen present along the surface can be substituted by chlorine even under optimum conditions.

A considerable amount of work has been done in recent years on formation and properties of carbon-oxygen surface complexes¹⁻³ and has been nicely reviewed⁴⁻⁶, but comparatively very little work has been done on carbon-halogen systems. It has been shown recently that treatment of charcoal with chlorine in aqueous solution involves surface oxidation rather than chlorination⁷ and that the treatment with bromine or iodine in aqueous solution involves both surface oxidation and halogenation¹⁰. The work of Ruff¹¹, who studied the interaction of activated charcoals and carbon blacks with chlorine gas at high temperatures, that of Reyerson and Wishart¹², who determined isotherms of chlorine on activated charcoals at temperatures varying from 35° to 91.5°, that of Alekseevskii and Likharev¹³, who activated a wide variety of charcoals by treatment with chlorine gas at 750-950°, and that of Boehm *et al.*¹⁴, who treated carbon blacks at 400-500°, show that a certain amount of the gas, which may in some cases be as much as 17% on the weight of the charcoal or carbon black, is retained and can neither be eliminated on boiling with alkali, nor on heating in vacuum, nor by electrodiolysis.

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The exact manner in which such a large amount of chlorine can be fixed on the carbon surface has not been properly elucidated. It is not known, for instance, whether the fixation of chlorine takes place by substitution in place of hydrogen (present in most carbons) or by addition at some unsaturated sites created on elimination of surface-oxygen complexes. The effect of temperature on the reaction also needs careful examination. There is one other aspect worthy of attention. Most carbons contain chemically bonded hydrogen which is so firmly fixed that its desorption commences only on heating in vacuum at 600° and is not completed even on raising the temperature^{1,15} to 1200°. It is not certain whether the hydrogen is uniformly distributed along the surface or a part of it is held within the interior of the carbon granules in one or more internal layers. A careful study of the interaction of charcoal and chlorine gas is expected to give some insight into this problem as well.

The present work was undertaken with the above objectives in view.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sugar charcoal, prepared by carbonisation of recrystallised cane sugar by means of pure sulphuric acid followed by exhaustive washings with hot distilled water, having negligible ash content (0.04%), was used as such (when it is referred to as 'original charcoal' in the text) and after evacuation at 400°, 500°, 700°, 1000°, and 1200°. The amounts of combined oxygen and hydrogen and their dispositions were determined by outgassing each sample (1 g.) at 1200° in a resistance tube furnace, estimating water by absorption in calcium chloride tubes, carbon dioxide in barium hydroxide solution contained in a series of Erlenmeyer flasks, and carbon monoxide in cuprous chloride solution contained in an Orsat-Lunge gas analysis apparatus. Since elementary hydrogen could not be removed completely on degassing at 1200°, its amount was determined by ultimate analysis after making due correction for the amount of water contained in the sample, where necessary. The results are recorded in Table I. It is evident that the samples differed appreciably in their oxygen and hydrogen contents.

TABLE I

Combined oxygen and hydrogen obtained on degassing each sample at 1200°.

Sample.	Combined oxygen evolved as.			*Total combined oxygen.	Elementary hydrogen.
	CO ₂ .	CO.	H ₂ O.		
Original	11.34	9.25	11.93	32.52	3.38
400°-degassed	4.75	7.14	4.97	16.86	3.37
500°-degassed	3.55	5.58	3.63	12.76	3.07
700°-degassed	2.91	4.57	Nil	7.48	2.58
1000°-degassed	Nil	1.42	Nil	1.42	1.15
1200°-degassed	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	1.02

N. B. Amounts expressed in g./100 g.

*Evolved as CO₂, CO and H₂O.

Chlorine Treatment

The charcoal sample (oven-dried at 120°) (10 g.) was taken in a silica glass tube of 3/4" bore which could be heated in a tube furnace to any desired temperature up to 1200°. Chlorine, purified and dried, was led over the charcoal at the rate of one litre per hour for different intervals of time, varying from 1 to 8 hours. The tube was kept rotating at the rate of 30-35 revolutions per minute to keep the charcoal in constant tumbling motion.

The gas coming out of the reaction tube was passed first through calcium chloride tubes to absorb the released water vapour and then through a series of Erlenmeyer flasks, three-fourth filled with CO₂-free distilled water and wrapped in thick black papers, for absorption of excess of chlorine as well as HCl gas formed during the interaction. The amount of each was determined by the usual analytical methods. Blank runs, without the charcoal, had shown that when chlorine was led through the tube into water under similar conditions, no HCl formed.

There was no indication for the formation of carbon tetrachloride or any other volatile chlorinated hydrocarbon during the treatment of any of the charcoals.

The chlorinated product, on cooling, was taken out of the tube and stored over nitrogen. About 1 g. of it was washed repeatedly with distilled water and the washings were titrated for free chlorine and HCl, if any. Usually, free chlorine was found absent. A small amount of HCl, nearly 3% of the amount obtained earlier in course of the treatment, was, however, recovered and added to the previous value.

The washed charcoal was dried at 120° in an air-oven and a small amount was taken for ultimate analysis.

The technique was checked in a few preliminary experiments by passing a known amount of chlorine over two different samples of charcoal (5 g. each) separately at 200° as well as at 400°. The amount of chlorine fixed, as obtained by difference, was seen to be quite close to the value determined by ultimate analysis (Table II).

TABLE II

Quantitative studies of the reaction between chlorine and charcoal.

Samples.	Treated at.	Cl ₂ passed*.	Chlorine obtained as.		*Chlorine fixed.	
			HCl gas.	Unchanged Cl ₂ .	(By diff.).	(By analysis)
Original charcoal	200°	400 m.c.	92.1 m.c.	267.8 m.c.	20.1 m.e./g.	19.4 m.e./g.
Do	400°	400	119.8	250.4	29.8	31.5
1200°-degassed charcoal	400°	400	23.9	364.5	11.6	12.3

*Per 5 g. charcoal.

DISCUSSION

The amounts of HCl gas formed and chlorine fixed on treatment of the original charcoal with chlorine at 400° for different intervals of time are shown graphically in Fig. 1. It is seen that each reaction tends towards an end point after about 5 to 6 hours. In all subsequent experiments therefore, the treatment was extended for a period of 6 hours only.

FIG. 1. Amounts of HCl formed and chlorine fixed on treating original charcoal with chlorine at 400°.

The amounts of chlorine fixed by the various samples of charcoal at 400° under similar conditions are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Amounts of chlorine fixed and HCl formed on treating the various charcoals with chlorine at 400°.

Samples.	Chlorine fixed.	HCl gas formed.
Original charcoal	6.70 m.e./g.	23.06 m.e./g.
400°-degassed	5.35	21.35
500°-degassed	4.21	7.40
700°-degassed	2.87	7.13
1000°-degassed	2.70	6.20
1200°-degassed	2.57	5.06

It is significant that removal of oxygen complexes on degassing (Table I), which is known to create unsaturated sites where oxygen or bromine from aqueous solution can be added up,¹⁰ does not cause any increase in the amount of chlorine fixed. On the contrary, the value decreases considerably on degassing at increasing temperatures. This may be due to progressive decrease in the hydrogen content of the charcoal on degassing at increasing temperatures (Table I). It appears highly probable that chlorine is fixed on charcoal by substitution rather than by addition. The amount of chlorine fixed by the original charcoal, when calculated otherwise, amounts to 237.8 mg./g., which is quite a high value. This chlorine could not be desorbed even on boiling with water or a solution of sodium hydroxide.

It is also seen (Table III) that HCl gas formed is considerably in excess of the chlorine fixed in every case. Apparently, only a small amount of the acid formed can be taken as due to the substitution reaction. The rest of it arises from direct combination of chlorine with hydrogen, given out by the charcoal during the treatment, and by interaction with chemisorbed water, if present. The samples degassed at 700°, 1000°, and 1200° did not contain any chemisorbed water (cf. Table I). Therefore HCl formed in these samples could be compared with the amount of hydrogen eliminated from the charcoal. This has been shown in Table IV where the loss of elementary hydrogen during the treatment is of about the same order as HCl formed. An appreciable amount of hydrogen, however, is still retained by the charcoal even after prolonged treatment with chlorine at 400°. It appears therefore that the elementary hydrogen, bonded in charcoal, behaves, as under, when the charcoal is treated with chlorine:

- (i) A part is substituted by chlorine, forming carbon-chlorine instead of carbon-hydrogen complex. An equivalent amount of HCl gas results.
- (ii) Another part is desorbed as such and combines with chlorine to form HCl gas.
- (iii) The rest of it is still retained by the charcoal.

This behaviour indicates that hydrogen in charcoal is not uniformly held. This aspect has been referred to (*vide infra*).

TABLE IV

HCl formed and loss of hydrogen on treating 700°, 1000°, and 1200°-outgassed charcoals with chlorine at 400°.

Samples.	HCl formed.	Loss of elementary hydrogen during the treatment.	Elementary hydrogen still retained by the charcoal.
700°-degassed charcoal	7.13 m.e./g.	8.0 m.e./g.	17.8 m.e./g.
1000°-degassed charcoal	6.20	6.0	4.6
1200°-degassed charcoal	5.06	0.7	3.5

Since chlorine was passed over the charcoal continuously, its concentration may be considered to have remained constant. It can then be shown (Table V) that the reactions involving formation of HCl gas and fixation of chlorine, under the experimental conditions described here, follow monomolecular trends after the first 30 minutes or so, when steady state appears to set in.

TABLE V

Calculation of velocity constants of the reactions involved.

Time.	Kinetics of the formation of HCl.			Kinetics of the fixation of chlorine.		
	Max. HCl formed	$a=22.00$ m.e./g.	*Velocity const.	Max. Cl ₂ fixed	$a=6.70$ m.e./g.	*Velocity const.
	HCl formed x .	$(a-x)$.		Chlorine fixed x .	$(a-x)$.	
30 min.	7.66 m.e./g.	15.00 m.e./g.	0.01296	3.00 m.e./g.	3.70 m.e./g.	0.01989
60	11.30	10.74	0.01197	4.16	2.60	0.01377
90	13.50	8.56	0.01055	5.00	1.70	0.01524
120	15.50	6.56	0.01015	5.60	1.10	0.01501
150	18.00	4.50	0.01127	6.00	0.70	0.01506
180	19.25	2.81	0.01145	6.25	0.45	0.01501
210	20.25	1.81	0.01190	6.45	0.25	0.01561
240	21.00	1.00	0.01264	6.55	0.15	0.01584

$$*K = \frac{2.303}{t} \log_{10} \frac{a}{(a-x)}$$

FIG. 2. Effect of temperature on the fixation of chlorine on the various samples of charcoal.

The effect of temperature on the fixation of chlorine as well as formation of HCl in case of the various samples of charcoal is shown in Figs. 2 and 3. It is seen that each reaction takes place to an appreciable extent even at 30° and that it is strongly tempera-

ture-dependent up to 400-500°. Arrhenius plots, based on the assumption that specific reaction rate is proportional to the reciprocal of temperature, provide activation energy for the temperature range 200-300°, varying from 3 to 4 kcal./mole, for the fixation of chlorine.

FIG. 3. Effect of temperature on the formation of hydrochloric acid on treatment of the various samples of charcoal with chlorine.

The optimum temperature for formation of HCl is seen to lie between 400° and 500°. There is little or no change on raising the temperature further.

The optimum temperature for formation of chlorine complex is also seen to lie between 400° and 500°. The values in case of the outgassed charcoals remain almost unchanged on raising the temperature to 700°. In the original charcoal, the value, however, decreases on raising the temperature to 500° and tends to become constant at 600°. The reason for the comparative instability of the complex in case of the original charcoal probably lies in the large amount of the CO₂-complex contained in the sample (Table I). As the temperature is raised beyond 400°, this complex decomposes, evolving a corresponding amount of carbon dioxide¹³ which is known¹⁶ to combine with chlorine at the prevailing temperature. It is highly probable that a part of the combined chlorine is eliminated in the atmosphere of carbon dioxide.

In order to ascertain the mode of distribution of hydrogen in the charcoal, the amount of elementary hydrogen, eliminated from the original charcoal on outgassing as well as on treatment with chlorine at different temperatures up to 1200°, was determined. The results are plotted graphically in Fig. 4. It is seen in the first place that heat treat-

ment in vacuum becomes effective to an appreciable extent only at temperatures above 500° and that above 1000° the curve tends to become asymptotic, showing that it becomes increasingly difficult to drive out residual hydrogen. Nearly 1.02 m.e., representing about one third of the hydrogen, is seen retained even on outgassing the charcoal at 1200°. These observations indicate that hydrogen is not uniformly held or distributed in the charcoal.

FIG. 4. Elimination of hydrogen from the original charcoal on (a) outgassing and (b) chlorine treatment at various temperatures.

The treatment with chlorine is seen to be far more effective. The elimination starts even at 30° and as much as 30% of the total is eliminated. At 100° over 55% (about 19 m.e. out of a total of 33.8 m.e.) is eliminated. The treatments at 200° and 300° do not cause any further significant decrease. Further noticeable elimination of hydrogen begins when the temperature of chlorination is raised to 400°; raising the temperature to 900°

makes no further improvement. Beyond that the elimination of hydrogen starts again and proceeds fairly rapidly with rise in temperature and is carried to near completion at 1200°.

These observations, particularly the stepwise elimination of hydrogen by chlorine treatments, are highly significant, indicating that hydrogen is bonded at different levels of energy, which are not continuous. Alternatively, it appears that only a part of the hydrogen is present along the surface and that the rest of it is present in more than one layers within the interior of the particles.

Taking 425 m²/g. as surface area of this charcoal¹⁷ and assuming that each surface carbon atom¹ occupies 2.6 Å², the number of carbon atoms on the surface can be shown to be equal to 1.64×10^{22} . As nearly 19 m.e. of hydrogen per g. of charcoal appears to come out at the first step on treatment with chlorine up to 100°; this amount may be taken as present along the surface of the charcoal which requires the lowest energy for desorption. The number of hydrogen atoms on the surface can then be shown by simple calculation to be equal to 1.15×10^{22} . According to this view therefore, the ratio of hydrogen to surface carbon atoms is roughly 7 to 10. In other words, nearly 70% of the surface carbon atoms is associated with one atom of hydrogen each. This seems to be a reasonable figure, keeping in view the fact that an appreciable amount of oxygen must also be present on the surface of this charcoal.

The rest of the hydrogen, which is driven out on raising the temperature in more than one step, must be present within the interior of the charcoal particles in more than one layers.

It is also evident that only a small amount of the surface hydrogen can be substituted by chlorine even under optimum conditions.

The stability and properties of the charcoal containing the chlorine complex will be reported in a subsequent communication.